

STUDY OF SOLUTION OF MAGNESIUM CHLORATE-GUANIDINE SULPHATE-WATER SYSTEM

Shakarov Norboy Jumayevich¹, Nomirov Maxsidin Nosirovich², Ergashev Isomiddin
Shodiyarovich³

^{1,2,3}Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction

Abstract. The solubility of magnesium chlorate, guanidine sulfate in aqueous solutions was studied visually-polythermally in the temperature range of 52.4 to 40 °C. X-ray phase, infrared spectrum, derivatographic analysis methods were used to determine the composition and structure of the substances formed in the system. A structural formula corresponding to the new substance guanidine chlorate was proposed.

Keywords: Magnesium chlorate, guanidine sulfate, guanidine chlorate, visual-polythermal method, solubility diagram, X-ray phase, infrared spectrum, derivatographic analysis methods.

Introduction

The main direction of the development of the economy of our republic is to achieve a sharp increase in the national economy and, on this basis, to further improve the well-being of the population through the rapid development of all sectors and the acceleration of scientific and technological progress.

Cotton growing in our country is one of the important branches of agriculture. To date, the primary goal of technical progress in cotton growing is mechanized harvesting, and in its implementation, chemical cleaning of cotton from leaves using chemical means before harvesting plays an extremely important role. Without this important agrotechnical measure, it is impossible to achieve high productivity of harvesters and success in cotton growing at the current stage of cotton cultivation.

Harvesting the cotton crop without leaving it for the rainy days of autumn is an important agrotechnical measure, and high-quality chemicals that ensure the artificial shedding of cotton leaves are widely used. Although they are highly effective in defoliation, they pollute the cotton crop due to dried leaves, reduce the germination rate of seeds, and spray large amounts of chemicals due to the small percentage of the active substance in the working solution, which has a negative impact on the ecological situation. Guanidine salts have an antiauxin effect, under their influence the “aging” process in plants accelerates, cotton leaves turn yellow and fall off. The creation of defoliant from chlorate chemicals and guanidine salts, which are used in low doses, have a high efficiency, and have a gentle effect on cotton leaves, is one of the urgent problems that our growers are waiting for a solution. To this end, the subject of our scientific research was the study of magnesium chlorate and guanidine sulfate salts in aqueous solutions by the visual-polythermal method.

$\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_3)_2 - [\text{NH}_2\text{C}(\text{NH})\text{NH}_2] * \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ The system was studied by conducting nine internal sections in the temperature range from -52.4 to 40 °C (Table 1). The polymer diagram of the system shows ice, guanidine sulfate, $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_3)_2 * 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_3)_2 * 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_3)_2 * 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{MgSO}_4 * 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the concentrations of the initial substances and the system temperature values that characterize the formation are determined. Due to the low

solubility of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the precipitation limit occupies the main part of the diagram, that is, the following exchange reaction occurs.

$\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the guanidine chlorate compound was isolated in the solid state by isothermal evaporation of the precipitated solution and analyzed for its identification by chemical elements and X-ray phase analysis. Thermal properties were studied using thermogravimetric methods, and the structure was studied using infrared spectral methods. $\text{NH}_2\text{C}(\text{NH})\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{HClO}_3$ the results of chemical analysis for the substance represented by the formula %.

	ClO_3^-	C	H	N
Calculated	58,3	8,29	4,1	2
	1		6	9,24
Experimentally determined	58,1	8,36	4,3	2
	9		9	9,27

According to X-ray diffraction analysis, guanidine chlorate has a crystalline structure, and in the X-ray diffraction pattern, diffraction reflexes at 3.74; 2.94; 2.42; 2.16; 1.64; 1.50; 1.44; 1.39; 1.34 Å are observed, which are not characteristic of the original substances.

The thermal stability of the guanidine chlorate salt was studied. During heating, three thermoeffects occur, which correspond to the processes of liquefaction and decomposition of the substance. The decomposition occurs in two stages: the first is exothermic, the second is endothermic. Thermogravimetric analysis of the dori and togram shows that the mass change during the decomposition of the substance by exothermic and endothermic effects is 100%, that is, the substance decomposes without residue.

Secondary and tertiary points of the magnesium chlorate-guanidine sulfate-water system

Table 1.

Mg (ClO_3) ₂	2 $\text{NH}_2\text{CNHNH}_2 \cdot$ H_2SO_4	H_2O	Crystallization, $t^\circ\text{C}$	Solid phase
-	57	43,0	-12,0	Ice + $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_3)_2$
36,9	-	63,1	-52,0	Ice + $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_3)_2 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$
42,0	-	58,0	-21,7	Ice + $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_3)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$
45,4	-	54,6	-7,5	Ice + $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
2,6	56,0	41,4	-13,6	Ice + $\text{NH}_2\text{CNHNH}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$
2,3	60,6	37,1	-3,0	$\text{NH}_2\text{CNHNH}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 +$ $[\text{NH}_2\text{CNHNH}_2]_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$
1,8	69,0	29,2	23,0	-/-
5,6	52,0	42,4	-15,8	Ice + $\text{NH}_2\text{CNHNH}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$
11,4	35,6	53,0	-13,6	-/-
19,0	19,0	64,0	-18,0	-/-
28,2	5,0	66,8	-31,6	-/-
34,8	2,6	62,6	-48,7	-/-
7,3	46,7	46,0	-14,3	Ice + $\text{NH}_2\text{CNHNH}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$

48,0	10,0	42,0	8,0	Mg(ClO ₃) ₂ *6H ₂ O + NH ₂ CNHNH ₂ * H ₂ SO ₄
46,8	6,8	47,4	1,2	-//-
43,2	3,0	53,8	-16,4	Mg(ClO ₃) ₂ *12H ₂ O + NH ₂ CNHNH ₂ * H ₂ SO ₄
45,0	4,2	50,8	-8,0	Mg(ClO ₃) ₂ *12H ₂ O + Mg(ClO ₃) ₂ *6H ₂ O + NH ₂ CNHNH ₂ * H ₂ SO ₄
41,6	2,5	55,9	-22,1	Mg(ClO ₃) ₂ *16H ₂ O + Mg(ClO ₃) ₂ *12H ₂ O + NH ₂ CNHNH ₂ * H ₂ SO ₄
36,6	2,0	61,4	-52,4	Ice + Mg(ClO ₃) ₂ *16H ₂ O + NH ₂ CNHNH ₂ * H ₂ SO ₄
4,4	55,0	50,6	-16,8	Ice + NH ₂ CNHNH ₂ *H ₂ SO ₄ + [NH ₂ CNHNH ₂] ₂ *H ₂ SO ₄
5,4	69,2	25,4	35,8	NH ₂ CNHNH ₂ *H ₂ SO ₄ + [NH ₂ CNHNH ₂] ₂ *H ₂ SO ₄
7,4	68,0	24,6	40,0	-//-
3,4	69,6	27,0	28,0	-//-

Guanidine exhibits strong basic properties. It contains amino and imino groups. In order to determine to which group the chloric acid proton is attached, the infrared spectra of the guanidine chlorate compound were studied.

The intense absorption lines belonging to the γ (C=N-) group around 1510 cm⁻¹ disappear from the infrared spectrum of guanidine chlorate. Based on this information, the imino group in the guanidine molecule is protonated (i.e., it binds an H⁺ ion), and as a result, the electrons of the C=N bond are delocalized.

In fact, the protonation of the imino functional group practically forms a stable cation. Since it stabilizes the positive charge in the hybrid ion, all nitrogen atoms participate in it in an equal contribution.

If protonation of the amino functional group is observed, the following process occurs:

A small number of nitrogen atoms participate in stabilizing the charge of the resulting hybrid ion, that is, the degree of stability of the hybrid ion is high. In the infrared spectrum of guanidine chlorate salt, there are absorption lines around 3400 and 3270 cm⁻¹, which correspond to the frequencies of the asymmetric γ As (NH₂) and symmetric γ s (NH₂) vibrations of the amino group. This means that the amino groups in the guanidine chlorate

molecule are preserved unchanged. Based on the data obtained, the following structural formula can be proposed for guanidine chlorate

Conclusion. The results of the study show that when using 70% magnesium chlorate and 80% guanidine sulfate solutions, the yield of guanidine chlorate formation is high, and its share in the product composition is 58.27%. It can be used in the preparation of a working solution of cotton defoliant.

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